

PARAMETRIC MODELING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Many models in polymer processing and composites manufacturing are defined in degenerated three-dimensional domains. By degenerated we understand that at least one of the characteristic dimensions of the domain is much lower than the other ones. This situation is particularly common in models defined in plate or shells type geometries.

When computing elastic response of plates, two dimensional plate theories are usually preferred to the numerically expensive solution of the full three-dimensional elastic problem. Going from a 3D elastic problem to a 2D plate theory model usually involves some kinematical and/or mechanical hypotheses on the evolution of the solution through the thickness of the plate.

Despite the quality of existing plate theories, their solution close to the plate edges is usually wrong as the displacement field are truly 3D in those regions and do not satisfy the kinematic hypothesis. Indeed, the kinematic hypothesis is a good approximation where Saint-Venant's principle is verified. However, some heterogeneous complex plates don't verify the Saint Venant's principle nowhere. In that case the solution of the three-dimensional model is mandatory even if its computational complexity could be out of the nowadays calculation capabilities.

Moreover, in the case of elastic behaviors the derivation of such 2D reduced models is quite simple and it constitutes the foundations of classical plate and shell theories. Today, most commercial codes for structural mechanics applications propose different type of plate and shell finite elements, even in the case of multilayered composites plates or shells. However, in composites manufacturing processes the physics encountered in such stratified plate or shell domains is much richer, because it

usually involves chemical reactions, crystallization and strongly coupled and non-linear thermomechanical behaviors. The complexity of the involved physics makes impossible the introduction of pertinent hypotheses for reducing a priori the dimensionality of the model from 3D to 2D. In that case a fully 3D modeling is compulsory, and because the richness of the thickness description (many coupled physics and many plies with different physical states and directions of anisotropy) the approximation of the fields involved in the models needs thousands of nodes distributed along the thickness direction. Thus, fully 3D descriptions may involve millions of degrees of freedom that should be solved many times because the history dependent thermomechanical behavior. Moreover, when we are considering optimization or inverse identification, many direct problems have to be solved in order to reach the minimum of a certain cost function.

Today, the solution of such fully 3D models remains intractable despite the impressive progresses reached in mechanical modeling, numerical analysis, discretization techniques and computer science during the last decade. New numerical techniques are needed for approaching such complex scenarios, able to proceed to the solution of fully 3D multiphysics models in geometrically complex parts (e.g. a whole aircraft). The well established mesh-based discretization techniques fail because the excessive number of degrees of freedom involved in the full 3D discretizations where very fine meshes are required in the thickness direction (despite its reduced dimension) and also in the in-plane directions to avoid too distorted meshes.

In this work we propose the application of the model reduction method known as Proper Generalized Decomposition - PGD- to the simulation of 3D thermomechanical models defined in plate geometries. This technique was proposed in two

recent papers [1,2] for circumventing, or at least alleviating, the curse of dimensionality. This method is based on the use of separated representations. It basically consists in constructing by successive enrichment an approximation of the solution (defined in a space of dimension d) in the form of a finite sum of N functional products involving d functions of each coordinate. In contrast with the shape functions of classical discretization methods, these individual functions are unknown *a priori*. They are obtained by introducing the approximate separated representation into the weak formulation of the original problem and solving the resulting non-linear equations. If M nodes are used to discretize each coordinate, the total number of unknowns amounts to $N \times M \times d$ instead of the M^d degrees of freedom of classical mesh-based methods. Thus, the complexity of the method grows linearly with the dimension d of the space wherein the problem is defined, in vast contrast with the exponential growth of classical mesh-based techniques.

This strategy was successfully applied in our studies of the kinetic theory description of complex fluids. A multidimensional separated representation of the linear steady-state Fokker-Planck equation was introduced in the seminal work [1], further extended to transient simulations in [2] and non-linear Fokker-Planck equations in [3]. In [4] we considered the solution of Fokker-Planck equations in complex flows, where space, time and conformation coordinates coexist.

The fully three-dimensional solution of models defined in degenerate domains is also an appealing field of application of the PGD. Consider the temperature field $u(x, y, z)$ defined in a plate domain Ξ . We could perform an in-plane-out-of-plane separated representation:

$$u(x, y, z) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{i=N} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot Z_i(z) \quad (1)$$

with $\mathbf{x} = (x, y) \in \Omega \subset \mathfrak{R}^2$ and $z \in I \subset \mathfrak{R}$. This strategy is particularly suitable when $\Xi = \Omega \times I$. More complex domains (e.g. plates with a varying thickness) can be treated by using an appropriate change of variable.

Because such decomposition involves the calculation of 2D functions $X_i(\mathbf{x})$ and 1D functions $Z_i(z)$ only (these ones with a computational complexity negligible with respect to the computation of the 2D functions), we can conclude that the computational complexity of the fully 3D solution scales like the complexity of 2D models.

2 In-plane-out-of-plane separated representation

In what follows we illustrate the construction of the Proper Generalized Decomposition of a model defined in a plate domain $\Xi = \Omega \times I$ with $\Omega \subset \mathfrak{R}^2$ and $I = [0, H]$ for the steady state heat transfer equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla u) = 0 \quad (2)$$

We consider that the laminate is composed of P different anisotropic plies each one characterized by a well defined conductivity tensor $\mathbf{K}_i(x, y)$ that is assumed constant in the ply thickness. Moreover, and without any loss of generality, we assume the same thickness for the different laminate layers, that we denotes by h . Thus, we can define a characteristic function representing the position of each layer $i = 1, \dots, P$:

$$\chi_i(z) = \begin{cases} 1 & z_i \leq z \leq z_{i+1} \\ 0 & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $z_i = (i-1) \times h$. Now, the laminate conductivity can be given in the following separated form:

$$\mathbf{K}(x, y, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=P} \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \chi_i(z) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = (x, y) \in \Omega$. The weak form of Eq. (2) reads:

$$\int_{\Xi} \nabla u^* \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla u) d\Xi = 0 \quad (5)$$

with the test function u^* in an appropriate functional space. The solution $u(x, y, z) \equiv u(\mathbf{x}, z)$ is searched under the separated form:

$$u(\mathbf{x}, z) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{i=N} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot Z_i(z) \quad (6)$$

In what follows we show the construction of one such a decomposition. For this purpose we assume that at iteration $n < N$ the solution $u^n(\mathbf{x}, z)$ is already known:

$$u^n(\mathbf{x}, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot Z_i(z) \quad (7)$$

and that at the present iteration we look for the solution enrichment $R(\mathbf{x}) \cdot S(z)$:

$$u^{n+1}(\mathbf{x}, z) = u^n(\mathbf{x}, z) + R(\mathbf{x}) \cdot S(z) \quad (8)$$

The test function involved in the weak form is assumed to be:

$$u^*(\mathbf{x}, z) = R^*(\mathbf{x}) \cdot S(z) + R(\mathbf{x}) \cdot S^*(z) \quad (9)$$

By introducing Eqs. (8) and (9) into (5) we obtain a non linear problem involving the unknowns $R(\mathbf{x}), S(z)$.

Now, as the enrichment process is non-linear we propose to search the couple of functions $R(\mathbf{x})$ and $S(z)$ by applying an alternating direction fixed point algorithm. Thus, assuming $R(\mathbf{x})$ known, we compute $S(z)$, and then we similarly update $R(\mathbf{x})$. The process continues until reaching convergence. The converged solutions allow defining the next term in the finite sums decomposition: $R(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow X_{n+1}(\mathbf{x})$ and $S(z) \rightarrow Z_{n+1}(z)$.

Discussion. We are comparing the complexity of PGD-based solvers with respect to the standard finite element method. For the sake of simplicity we will consider a hexahedral domain discretized using a regular structured grid with respectively N_x , N_y and N_z nodes in the x , y and z directions respectively. Even if the domain thickness is much lower than the other characteristic in-plane dimensions, the physics in the thickness direction could be quite rich, mainly when we consider

composites plates composed of hundreds of plies in which the complex physics involved requires fully 3D descriptions. In that case thousands of nodes in the thickness direction could be required to represent accurately the solution behavior in that direction. In usual mesh-based discretization strategies this fact induces a challenging issue because the number of nodes involved in the model scales with $N_x \times N_y \times N_z$, however, if one applies a PGD based discretization, and the separated representation of the solution involves N modes (terms in the finite sum decomposition), one should solve N 2D problems related to the functions involving the in-plane coordinates and N 1D problems related to the functions involving the thickness coordinate. The computing time related to the solution of the one-dimensional problems can be neglected with respect to the one required for solving the two-dimensional ones. Thus, the PGD complexity scales as $N \times N_x \times N_y$.

By comparing both complexities we can notice that as soon as $N_z \gg N$ the use of PGD-based discretization leads to impressive computing time savings, making possible the solution of models never until now solved, even using low performance computing platforms.

3 Parametric modeling

However, the model just proposed must be solved as soon as the plies orientation changes. One possibility for solving only once the model, whose solution must be valid for any orientation of any ply, consists in writing the conductivity as:

$$\mathbf{K}(x, y, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=P} \mathbf{K}_i(\theta_i) \cdot \chi_i(z) \quad (10)$$

Where we assumed unidirectional homogeneous plies oriented in the direction given by θ_i and then a generalized solution is searched in the separated form:

$$u(\mathbf{x}, z, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_p) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{i=N} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot Z_i(z) \cdot \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \Theta_j^i(\theta_j) \right) \quad (11)$$

The thermal calculation can be coupled with a thermoelastic model solved by using again the in-plane-out-of-plane separated representation of each component of the displacement field.

For illustrating the approach capabilities we consider a laminate composed of 4 plies, and the orientation both external plies are considered as extra-coordinates. Now, by particularizing the general solution for different values of these orientations one can obtain an equilibrated laminate of different distorted laminates when the laminate is not perfectly equilibrated as depicted in Fig. 1. Because this particularization involves light calculation, it can be performed in light computation platforms as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Thermoelastic laminate deformation for different configurations: equilibrated (left) and non equilibrated (right).

Fig. 2. Thermoelastic laminate deformation for a non-equilibrated configuration.

4 Conclusions

The simulation of composites manufacturing processes remains today a challenging issue despite the recent impressive progresses in computational resources. The simulation of processes of industrial interest needs the proposal of advanced numerical strategies, radically different to the ones until now widely used, usually based on finite element, finite difference or finite volumes discretizations.

In this work we explored the potentiality of

techniques based on model reduction, and in particular those making use of the so-called Proper Generalized Decomposition. This technique allows circumventing the curse of dimensionality when addressing models defined in high dimensional spaces. We proved that it could constitute a real breakthrough for addressing shape or process optimization as well as inverse analysis.

On the other hand thanks to the separated representation that the PGD uses, full 3D solutions in plate domains could be achieved by separating the in-plane and out-of-plane (thickness) coordinates. Thus full 3D solutions could be computed by keeping a 2D computational complexity.

Thanks to this novel approach we solved models never until now solved, without the necessity of using powerful computing platforms. Many solutions can be achieved by using Matlab and a laptop, and even light computing devices, as for example smartphones.

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